

WEST AFRICAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION AND PLANNING (WAJEAP)

VOL 1, NO. 1
ISSN: 3026-9202

**WEST AFRICAN JOURNAL OF
EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION
AND PLANNING (WAJEAP)**

ISSN: 3026-9202

Vol. 1 , December, 2023

A Publication of

The University of Sierra Leone, Sierra Leone

Editorial Board

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. M.O.B. Mohammed

*Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education,
Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos Nigeria*

Email: mubashiru.mohammed@lasu.edu.ng

08033344750

Consulting Editors

1. Prof Jonas A S Redwood-Sawyerr,
*Executive Director, eLearning Centre,
University of Sierra Leone*
2. Prof Ronnie Frazer-Williams
*Dean, School of Postgraduate Studies,
University of Sierra Leone*
3. Onoriode Collins Potokri PhD
*Education Leadership and Management
Faculty of Education, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
cpotokri@uj.ac.za*
4. Prof Ayeni Abiodun Olumide
*University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria
Faculty of Education,
Department of Educational Management
Email: biodunmide@gmail.com*
5. Prof George Oduro
*University of Cape coast,
Institute for Educational Planning and Administration, Ghana
Email: goduro@ucc.edu.gh*

CONTENTS

The Use of Lichens as Bio-Indicators and a Cost-Effective way for Heavy Metals Pollution Monitoring in Ambient Air in The Western Area and Southern Province of Sierra Leone Abdul Sannoh & Ronnie. A.D. Frazer-Williams -----	1-13
Academic Mentorship and Lecturers' Productivity in Public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria SHITTU, Taofeek Olawale; OLA, Bolanle Adeyemi & ADEPOJU, Funke Femi -----	14-20
Paradoxes of the use of Technologies in Secondary Education System in Africa Femi Sunday Akinwumi & Adeola Iyabosola Ayo-Ayinde -----	21-30
Social Insecurity and Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome among Adolescents in Lagos State, Nigeria: Counselling for National Development A. O. Badejo & Stella Ngozi Chinwuba-Anameje -----	31-40
Design and Production of an Improved Cook Stove with Swinging Combustion Chamber to Enable Refueling for Continuous Operation Sheriff Kamara -----	41-59
Teachers' Welfare as a Veritable Tool for Effectiveness among Public Secondary Schools In Lagos State, Nigeria Ladipo, Sunday Akinremi -----	60-63
Free Education Program in Sub Saharan Africa: A Comparative Analysis of Sierra Leone and Nigeria James VIBBI & Abidat Oluwashola MOHAMMED -----	64-76
Managing Education for Innovation and Security in the Development of Sub-Shara Africa: Policy Formulation and Implementation Option John Oluyemi EGBEBI & Opeyemi Aderonke OYEKAN -----	77-85
Cross-Cultural Influences on Girl-Child Education in Ojo Riverine Area of Lagos State, Nigeria Enitan Omolara Falade & Prof. Olawunmi Ayodeji Badejo -----	86-92
Establishing a School Climate That Prioritizes Child Safety to Promote Sustainable National Development Henry Adewale Odunayo; Nurudeen Olalekan Orunbon & M. O. B. Mohammed -----	93-102
Gender Equality: A Must for Sustainable Development in Africa Aisha Fofana Ibrahim & Claudine Anita Hingston -----	103-110
Teachers' Reward System and Academic Performance of Public Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos State, Nigeria ANIFOWOSHE, Olawale Jamiu & MOHAMMED, M. O. B. -----	111-116

Records Management Practices and Productivity of Academic Heads of Department in Public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria Afolabi, Abolanle Omotunde; Shittu, Taofeek Olawale & Mohammed, M. O. B. -----	117-124
Estimating Rainfall Intensity Duration-Frequency (IDF) Curves for River Rokel Catchment in Tonkolili District Using Satellite Rainfall Data Amadu Barrie; Osman Koroma & Melvin B Scott -----	125-135
Religious Education, Security Challenges, and National Development in Nigeria Exradallenum Olusegun Akinsanya, Opaaje, Samuel Sunday & Aina, Omololu Olukayode -----	136-147
Integrating Sustainable Water Resources Management Practices into Public University Administration in Lagos State, Nigeria: A Multi-Variable Analysis Adepoju, Funke Femi -----	148-155
Examining the Nexus between Inadequate Educational Facilities as Proxy for Migration and Personal Remittance in Nigeria: Impact on Socio-Economic Development Rufai, Musiliu Dada; Anagun, Adeyemi Michael & Olayide, Bilkis Omolara	156-165

ESTABLISHING A SCHOOL CLIMATE THAT PRORITIZES CHILD SAFETY TO PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Henry Adewale Odunayo

*Department of Economics Education,
Lagos State University of Education,
Oto-Ijanikin, Lagos State.
waleodunayo2002@yahoo.com*

Nurudeen Olalekan Orunbon

*Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education, Lagos State University.
nurudeen.orunbon@lasu.edu.ng*

M. O. B. Mohammed

*Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education, Lagos State University.
mubashiru.mohammed@lasu.edu.ng*

Abstract

When it comes to national development, a stable and secure society is essential. This is especially true for developing countries where the most vulnerable individuals are children. To ensure that sustainable national development can be achieved, it is important to establish a school climate that prioritizes child safety and well-being. This paper explores the ways in which school climate can be improved to create safer learning environments for children in developing countries. It examines various strategies for improving school climate, including introducing child safety protocols, providing access to psychological services, and establishing punishments for certain types of dangerous behavior. It also looks at the potential benefits that these strategies may have on overall national development. Overall, this paper concludes that in order to ensure sustainable national development, it is essential to establish a school climate that prioritizes child safety and well-being. Through the implementation of various strategies, children in developing countries can be empowered to reach their full potential without fear of harm or exploitation. By creating a safe and nurturing environment, the long-term outcomes of establishing a school climate that prioritizes child safety can lead to more successful national development.

Keywords: School Climate, Child Safety, National Development

Introduction

Education at all levels and in all its forms constitutes a vital tool for addressing virtually all global problems. Education is not only an end in itself. It is a key instrument for bringing about changes in knowledge, values and behaviours and life styles required to achieve sustainability and stability within and among countries (Bajaj & Chiv, 2009). Education has been seen as the greatest force that can be used to bring about changes. Aminu (1995) observed that the greatest investment a nation can make for the development of its economic, sociological and human resources is that of education.

Education has been conceptualized in various ways by scholars. According to United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) (2000), "education refers to the total process of developing human ability and behaviours". It is an organized and sustained instruction designed to communicate a combination of knowledge, skills and understanding value for all activities of life. Education refers to what can be used by man to solve his problems to improve his life and make it comfortable. It is also a formidable tool for man's survival.

Apart from the concept of "Development", the Bruntland Commission shifted the attention by reshaping and modifying the concept to "Sustainable Development." The most interesting aspect of sustainable development is the fact that it puts in to consideration the present conditions of people as well as not compromising those that come later. Therefore, the concept of sustainable national Development remains the modern parameter of measuring development. The Bruntland Commission, (1987) defined sustainable Development as "the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs." In another definition by Munasinghe (2004), sustainable national Development is a process of improving the range of opportunities that will enable individual humans and communities to achieve their aspirations and full potential over a sustained period of time while maintaining the resilience of economic, social and environmental systems. Age (2005), identified some objectives which sustainable national development is expected to realize: increase capital income and employment, promoting human welfare satisfying basic needs; protecting the environment. Considering the path of future generation, achieving equity between rich and poor and participation on a broad basis in development and decision making is important.

Education and Sustainable National Development: The Relationship

More countries are recognizing education for sustainable development as an integral part of quality education and a key factor for sustainable development itself. The reorientation of pedagogic education towards sustainability is a pervasive trend. Education for sustainable development is the contribution of the world's education, public awareness, and learning systems to the path of humanity to a more sustainable future (Malolitneva, 2020; Orloviclovren, Maruna & Stanarevic, 2020). Sustainable development in simple terms is perceived as an integral resultant interaction of human health and well-being, a sustainable economy (including poverty reduction, consumption, and waste management), and a sustainable environment, ensuring high quality of life for the population.

From the above the various definitions of education and sustainable national development, it is imperative to examine the relationship between the two concepts. In all nations, Nigeria inclusive, education remains the instrument for effective national development. Development is championed through education, which is often assumed to have significant influence. Education entails the enlightenment of people in their ways of pursuit in life. Development is associated with a positive change in the condition of either individual groups, communities or even a country as a whole (Umoh, 2005). Education and sustainable national development are interwoven, intertwined, and interconnected. While on the one hand, development is geared towards producing or creating something new or more advanced for the society and its members.

On the other hand, education is a tool which can enhance the desired sustainable development. Umoh, 2005 therefore, refers education and sustainable development as two

sides of the same coin. The fact that education and sustainable development shows glaring connectivity probably explained why scholars emphasized the need for education for the purpose of achieving the desired sustainable development. Ebong (1996) sees education as a systematic procedure for the transfer and transformation of culture through formal and informal training of people in the society. He further stated that “the goal of education in man power development is aimed at national growth and development” (Ebong 1996). For any country therefore, to attain sustainable national development, he concluded that “there is need for skilled man power and those skills required are basic ingredients for national development and can only be acquired through education” (Ebong 1996). It is also mentioned by Olubadewo (2006) that it is only educated population that can command skills necessary for sustainable economic growth and a better quality of life. It is important to note therefore that education cannot translate to sustainable national development with prioritizing the child safety.

Security in the broadest sense characterizes a stable way of being an object, the preservation of its identity in the face of internal and external negative influences. Ensuring security expresses the possibility and ability of an object for self-preservation and further evolutionary self-organization under negative influences, threats, and dangers. Security is always associated with the preservation of an object and development - with its change. It should be noted that security is one of the conditions for a child's self-fulfillment, an educational environment that enables the child to fulfill himself and transfer to sustainable development. Conflicts, environmental, financial, health and humanitarian crises place children at risk of multiple rights violations, violence, marginalization, and discrimination. More than half of children and adolescents do not meet minimum literacy and numeracy standards (UNESCO, 2020), and an estimated 250 million children under 5 in low- and middle-income countries may not reach developmental potential (The Lancet Commissions, 2020).

Each year in the United States, 46 million children are exposed to violence, crime, abuse, or psychological trauma, as well as homelessness and food insecurity. Experiencing these types of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) creates toxic stress that affects attention, learning, and behavior. Poverty and racism, together and separately, make the experience of chronic stress and adversity more likely. Furthermore, in schools where students encounter punitive discipline tactics rather than supports for handling adversity, their stress is magnified. In addition to meeting basic needs for food and health care, schools can buffer the effects of stress by facilitating supportive adult-child relationships that extend over time; building a sense of self-efficacy and control by teaching and reinforcing social and emotional skills that help children handle adversity, such as the ability to calm emotions and manage responses; and creating dependable, supportive routines for both managing classrooms and checking in on student needs.

Because children learn when they feel safe and supported, and their learning is impaired when they are fearful, traumatized, or overcome with emotion, they need both supportive environments and well-developed abilities to manage stress. Therefore, it is important that schools provide a positive learning environment—also known as school climate—that provides support for learning social and emotional skills as well as academic content. Two recent reviews of research, incorporating more than 400 studies, have found that a positive school climate improves academic achievement overall and reduces the negative effects of poverty on achievement, boosting grades, test scores, and student engagement. The

elements of school climate contributing most to increased achievement are associated with teacher-student relationships, including warmth, acceptance, and teacher support. Other features include

- a. high expectations, organized classroom instruction, effective leadership, and teachers who are efficacious and promote mastery learning goals;
- b. strong interpersonal relationships, communication, cohesiveness, and belongingness between students and teachers; and
- c. structural features of the school, such as small school size, physical conditions, and resources, which shape students' daily experiences of personalization and caring.

Schools that effectively support their students create a learning culture and climate that are “both responsive to the changing needs of the individual and offer the kinds of stimulation that will propel continued positive growth.”

Strategies for Developing Productive School Environments

To support student achievement, attainment, and behavior, research suggests that schools should attend to four major domains, shown in Figure 2 and described below:

1. Building a positive school climate in both classrooms and the school as a whole
2. Shaping positive student behaviors through social and emotional learning
3. Developing productive instructional strategies that support motivation, competence, and self-directed learning
4. Creating individualized supports that address student needs, including the effects of trauma and adversity.

A Framework for Whole Child Education

Identity-Safe Classrooms Identity-safe classrooms promote student achievement and attachments to school. The elements of such classrooms, found to support strong academic performance for all students, include:

- a. Teaching that promotes understanding, student voice, student responsibility for and belonging to the classroom community, and cooperation in learning and classroom tasks.
- b. Cultivating diversity as a resource for teaching through regular use of diverse materials, ideas, and teaching activities along with high expectations for all students.
- c. Classroom relationships based on trusting, encouraging interactions between the teacher and each student, and the creation of positive relationships among the students.
- d. Caring, orderly, purposeful classroom environments in which social skills are proactively taught and practiced to help students respect and care for one another in an emotionally and physically safe classroom, so each student feels attached to the others.

The climate of a school has always been, and continues to be, essential to a school's success in educating its children and preparing them for a life beyond its corridors. In addition, a school that acknowledges the complexity inherent in its climate and takes clear steps toward creating one conducive to learning is a school that will inevitably become a safer school. There are seven important factors that contribute to a healthy school climate:

1. **Models:** Adults are teachers in more ways than one, and the way that has the greater impact is less what we say than what we do. We must act as good models, offering a balance between setting reasonable limits and providing opportunities for authentic choices, between holding up clear expectations for children to reach and extending a hand to help. Students who feel that they are noticed and valued are more motivated to work hard and care about themselves and others (Noddings 1996).

2. **Consistency:** The school staff must be vigilant in sending coherent and consistent messages to students and families. A school must be determined in its pursuit of teachers who are not only effective but project qualities that are most desirable in students: eagerness to learn, willingness to collaborate, and appreciation for diverse points of view, among others. The school that attracts such teachers and, more than that, then minimizes staff turnover is more likely to create an effective learning community.
3. **Depth:** It is important to build beyond—while not ignoring—first impressions. Mission statements, school pledges, and school wide rituals are important components of a school's climate, especially considering that they are often a visitor's first impression of the school. However, they certainly cannot stand alone, and if they are not held in place by more substantive structures reflected in resources such as books, songs, curriculum, and classroom rituals and practice—including critical reflection on group behavior—then the message sent by a mission statement will collapse quickly, revealing a hollow promise.
4. **Democracy:** Sharing power in an environment that has traditionally been structured as a top-down hierarchy can be a frightening and difficult transition, but a democratic classroom and school need not be a radical change. In order to become proficient leaders and decision-makers outside school, students require practice and guidance (Schimmel 1997). Educators should challenge themselves to create a democratic climate in their classrooms and in their schools, recognizing that shared decision making can take many guises.
5. **Community:** Most people working in a school will tell you that no school can ever have too much help. In fact, the less insular a school community is, the more positive its climate is likely to be. Traditionally, schools close their doors at the beginning of the school day and keep them closed until students come barreling out at the end of the day. However, families in particular, as well as such community members as neighbors, businesses, and other groups, have an investment in the success of the school. Communities are interdependent entities, and in order to maximize the many talents and shared stakes of community members, a school must open its doors and create opportunities for as many people as possible to become involved.
6. **Engagement:** Many skills are inherent in the practice of community service-learning. With the opportunity to identify problems and become agents of change, students take charge of a part of their education and in the process often alter the perception of adults both in and outside the school (Hart 1998). This reformed perspective—viewing children as problem solvers instead of problems—has the happy side effect of building students' sense of purpose and of what is possible. Creating a community of students empowered to make changes and emboldened by their own success contributes to a climate where service to others is valued and where that value has significant carryover.
7. **Leadership:** Engaging school staff, families, community members, and students in creating and maintaining a positive school climate requires a strong school administration supported by a core of staff and families. A successful administrator must be willing to take the risks necessary to transform a climate and provide ongoing support to those engaged in the process (Fullan 2002). Some of the most important roles of the administrator include articulating a shared vision and sense of purpose for those in the school and serving as a strong role model—from the way adults relate to children and families, to the way community members are invited and welcomed to the school, to the way decisions are made.

Child Safety

The term 'child safety/protection' refers to any action that aims to prevent, protect and respond to violence, exploitation and abuse against children. A child protection framework may include legislation and policies that provide specific rights for children, services that support the protection of children within communities. Child protection work also responds to violence including giving medical treatment, and processes to ensure victims can access justice.

United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) uses the term 'child protection' to refer to preventing and responding to violence, exploitation and abuse against children - including commercial sexual exploitation, trafficking, child labour and harmful traditional practices, such as female genital mutilation/cutting and child marriage. UNICEF's child protection programmes also target children who are uniquely vulnerable to these abuses; such as when living without parental care, in conflict with the law and in armed conflict. Violations of the child's right to protection take place in every country and are massive, under-recognized and under-reported barriers to child survival and development, in addition to being human rights violations. Children subjected to violence, exploitation, abuse and neglect are at risk of death, poor physical and mental health, HIV/AIDS infection, educational problems, displacement, homelessness, vagrancy and poor parenting skills later in life (UNICEF, 2005).

The Concept of Child

The African Charter defines anybody under the age of 18 years old as a child (Article 2), and includes a range of civil, political, economic, political, and social rights as expressed in other international human rights conventions but with a special focus on the needs of children or particular groups of children who are more likely to face human rights abuses. For example the convention includes protection around:

- a. The right to non-discrimination
- b. The right to life
- c. The right to religion
- d. Freedom of expression
- e. The right to privacy
- f. The right to education
- g. The right of every mentally or physically disabled child to receive special measures of protection
- h. The right to health Freedom from torture.

Why Prioritizing Child Safety to Promote Sustainable National Development

- a. It is estimated that 150 million girls and 73 million boys worldwide are raped or subjected to other forms of sexual violence each year.
- b. Since 1990, an estimated 90% of those killed in conflicts around the world have been civilians, and 80% of those have been women and children.
- c. In at least 13 countries, children are being recruited into armed forces and groups.
- d. It is estimated that between 100 and 140 million girls and women in the world have undergone some form of female genital mutilation.
- e. Among young women aged 15-24, 48% were married before the age of 18 in South Asia (9.7 million girls), 42% in Africa, and 29% in Latin America and the Caribbean.
- f. Some 17,700 asylum applications were lodged by unaccompanied or separated children in 69 countries in 2011, mostly by Afghan and Somali children.
- g. It is estimated that over 145 million children have lost one or both parents.

- h. Over 8 million children without appropriate care around the world live in residential care facilities.
- i. Around the world, 115 million children – 74 million boys and 41 million girls – are involved in the worst forms of child labour.
- j. Three out of four children experience violent discipline at home.
- k. 16.6 million children have lost one or both parents due to HIV and AIDS and have important care needs: 90% of those children live in sub-Saharan Africa.

Safety Challenges of School Children in Promoting Sustainable National Development

1. Challenges in physical facilities Physical infrastructure such as classrooms, offices, toilets, kitchen, water tanks, playground, and equipment among others should be appropriate, adequate and properly located to avoid any risks to users. The early childhood development service standards guidelines 2006 outlines various standards that should be observed when constructing classrooms for preschool children. Among them is to have a classroom measuring 8 by 6 metres accommodating a maximum of 25 children. The classroom should have proper roofing, windows, doors and flooring as well as adequate ventilation. The chairs should be child sized and age appropriate (Republic of Kenya, 2006).
2. Challenges in outdoor play space and equipment Outdoor space is critical in providing children with opportunities to play. To enhance proper utilisation, the space should be large enough to accommodate the number of children in the preschool, so that children can play and run freely without hurting each other. The early childhood development services standards guidelines 2006 outlines various standards related to children's outdoor play space, as well as play and learning equipment. According to the standards, outdoor play should be large enough to accommodate the number of children to play and run around. The surface of the play area should be free from sharp objects, harmful plants and discarded materials and equipment. The compound should be fenced and have a lockable gate to prevent children from sneaking out of school without teacher's notice, as well as for the security of children while in school.
3. Challenges with school compounds fencing the school compound is key in ensuring that children do not run in and out of school without the teachers' knowledge. This will ensure security of children and having a security officer to man the gate may be necessary. School grounds, according to the Kenya safety standards manual for schools, refers to the entire enclosure used by the school for learning, playing games or sports (Republic of Kenya, 2008). The grounds should be large enough to accommodate physical infrastructure including classrooms, offices, latrines, playing grounds and walkaways. Indicators of safe school grounds include properly reinforced fences with well fitted lockable gates; well maintained and clean learning rooms; and well maintained and clean desks and chairs in classrooms.
4. Challenges with firefighting equipment and first aid kits Children's safety while in school is of key importance. Ensuring that safety equipment such as firefighting and first aid kits are available is critical in any learning institution. Other safety measures would include having buckets full of sand, blankets or even water available for use in case of fire outbreak. The early childhood service standard guidelines 2006 requires each preschool to have fire extinguishers and buckets full of sand, blankets and water as a way of responding to fire outbreak in preschools. It further requires preschools to have first aid kits with required drugs, and to train members of staff on how to administer first aid to children in case of injury.

5. Challenges concerning water and sanitation Water, sanitation and hygiene are critical in promoting a conducive learning environment. Thus improving water, sanitation and hygiene in schools will enhance child health, attendance and retention, as well as performance. This will also help to reduce water borne and sanitation related diseases such as cholera, worms, skin infection and diarrhea (Republic of Kenya, 2011). The early childhood development services standards guidelines of 2006 requires preschools to have separate toilets for boys and girls at a ratio of 1:25, specially designed for young children. It further requires preschools to have safe water for use in the kitchens, for play activities, drinking and washing hands.

Conclusion

Each year many children worldwide die before their fifth birthday and those that do survive do not normally reach their full developmental potentials due to early exposure to some unfavourable conditions which interfere with their normal physical, intellectual and social development. Persistent hunger, lack of access to clean water, medical care and dirty places of domicile as well as over laboured are powerful factors jeopardizing children well-being in many developing countries, thus, children face high probability of early mortality, school failure; early pregnancy; joblessness; and costly diseases across their lifespan. This is therefore clear evidence to global loss of human potentials which in turn represents an enormous challenge to not only global sustainable development, but sustainable national development.

Recommendations

1. Qualified and experienced employees should be employed to take charge of the affairs of the kids to curb maltreatment, negligence, exploitation.
2. Nigerian government should establish a security outfit with powers to provide protection to children against every form of domestic activities that show tendencies of exposing children to hard labour so that children's moral, physical, mental, health and emotional development could be enhanced.
3. Government should encourage NGOs by financially assisting them in raising awareness through building capacity, abuse and rehabilitation centers, empowerment programmes such as vocational training.
4. NGOs should encourage and collaborate with relevant authorities particularly the government in providing substantial data, information and ideas on how to tackle child abuse menace so as to provide safety for them.
5. The National and states house of assembly should review the child right act legislation with a view to cubing child abandonment and abuse.
6. The living standards of the citizens should be improved so as to discourage child labour and child marriages.

References

- Brion-Meisels, S., & Selman, R. (1996). From Fight or Flight to Collaboration: Individual and Institutional Development in the School, in *Schools, Violence and Society*, ed. A. Hoffman. Westport, Conn.
- Charney, R. (1993). *Teaching Children to Care: Management in the Responsive Classroom*. Greenfield, Mass. Northeast Foundation for Children.
- Defence for Children International, 'No Kids Behind Bars: A global campaign on justice for children in conflict with the law.
- Education Commission of the States (ECS). June 2003. *Civic Engagement and Service-Learning with Young Children*. Intergenerational Peacemaking Projects.
- Fullan, M. (2002). The Change Leader. *Educational Leadership* 59(8): 16-21.
- Hart, R. (1998). *Children's Participation: The Theory and Practice of Involving Young Citizens in Community Development and Environmental Care*. London: Earthscan Publications.
- Noddings, N. (1996). Learning to Care and Be Cared For, in *Schools, Violence, and Society*, ed. A. Hoffman. Westport, Conn.
- Schimmel, D. (1997). Traditional Rule-making and the Subversion of Citizenship Education. *Social Education* 61(2): 70-74.
- Sustainable Development Goal 3, <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg3>.
- The Lancet Commissions (2020). *A future for the world's children? A WHO-UNICEF-Lancet Commission*. p. 611.
- United Nations Children Fund (UNICEF) (2020). *Child poverty*. <https://www.unicef.org/social-policy/child-poverty>.
- United Nations Children's Fund (2005). *Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting: A statistical exploration*. UNICEF, New York.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2020). <http://data.uis.unesco.org/?lang=en&SubSessionId=c254068b-d342-4926-82b6-3555c2b6840e&themetreeid=-200>.